

Fractal Dimension of Linear Network Segments: Experiments on Hiking Trails

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Abstract: Complex terrestrial linear networks like roads, rivers, and hiking trails have different degrees of spatial variation in different environments and across different geographic scales. Fractal dimension is a longstanding conceptual approach to characterizing such spatial variation over multiple scales, and a number of algorithms have been developed to calculate fractal dimension of a linear feature. In this paper, we develop, implement, and test a variant of the widely published box-counting algorithm that uses rasterization to make the process computationally efficient to run on datasets containing hundreds or thousands of high-spatial resolution linear features. This variant separately calculates fractal dimension in the horizontal and vertical dimensions. We then apply this variant on a dataset of over 300 randomly sampled segments of Slovenia's 10,000 km hiking trail network. Segments range from trails in gently varying terrain to routes in alpine regions with extremely steep and rough topography. Two methodological approaches were applied and compared: a raster-based R workflow and a vector-based ArcGIS Pro/Python workflow, the latter applied to a smaller subset of the dataset. Two main datasets were used: vector data representing hiking trails and a lidar derived digital terrain model (DTM) with a 1 m horizontal resolution, both covering the entirety of Slovenia. The two approaches were further tested and compared using five synthetic curves. Results show that, while like other box counting implementations, ours suffer from some inaccuracy, fractal dimensions in the horizontal and vertical dimensions provide useful insight into the variation in hiking trails in a wide range of conditions and offer promise for new approaches to classify trail difficulty.

Keywords: fractal dimension; box-counting; hiking trails; GIS; Slovenia.

1 Introduction

Spatial variation of linear features on the Earth's surface is interesting and important for geographic data scientists. This variation is challenging to measure (Dhara et al. 2022), offers clues about the natural and human processes that shape such features (Dhara et al. 2022, Liu et al. 2026), and affects a wide range of management decisions, including land use planning, infrastructure routing, and environmental risk assessment (Gabrielsen and Olesen 2024, Geoimage 2024). Spatial linear variation is scale-dependent at geographic scales, making measurement and modelling difficult. Fractal dimension has long been suggested as an appropriate means to measure linear complexity, and many methods for empirically calculating

it have been proposed (Klinkenberg 1994). For the past several years we have been conducting research on the fractal dimension of human-engineered linear features like roads and trails and developing different implementations to efficiently and accurately calculate it for large numbers of these features (Prah and Shortridge 2023, Prah 2024).

Here we report on an extended experiment on vertical and horizontal complexity of hiking trails. We calculate vertical and horizontal dimensions for a stratified random sample of 307 hiking trails across Slovenia. Slovenia provides an excellent place for this research, as its topography spans four geomorphic regions from relatively level plains to high-relief Alpine contexts. We identify the practical range of both vertical and horizontal fractal dimension for hiking trails and then consider whether trails can be usefully categorized by their values of vertical and fractal dimension.

2 Materials and methods

Two primary datasets were used in this study: vector data for hiking trails and the Digital Terrain Model (DTM), both covering all of Slovenia. The hiking trails dataset (Planinska zveza Slovenije, 2024) originated from unprojected GPX-format dataset, and therefore had to be converted into an ArcGIS Feature Class and transformed to the Slovenia 1996 National Grid projected coordinate system (EPSG: 3794). Point features were then converted into line features. The second dataset is the lidar-derived Slovenian national Digital Terrain Model with 1 m horizontal resolution (Ministry of Natural Resources and Spatial Planning, 2015).

2.1 Core Method

All Fractal dimension is an index for characterizing fractal patterns or sets by quantifying their complexity as a ratio of the change in detail to the change in scale. Mandelbrot (1967, 1983) extended the concept to describe natural forms, in which irregular structures exhibit recurring structural patterns and persistent geometric detail across multiple spatial scales. Fractal dimensions are non-integer values, reflecting intermediate degrees of complexity (Batty and Longley 1994, Jahanmiri 2015).

Several definitions and implementations of fractal dimension exist (Abid et al. 2021). Among these, the box-counting method (Gonzato 1998, Gonzato et al. 2000, Grassberger 1993) is the most widely used in applied spatial analysis. However, when estimating fractal dimension with box-counting algorithms, substantial variation in results has been documented due to grid spacing and the orientation between the grid and the linear

feature (Douglass 2025). Box-counting works as follows: an object is covered with a grid of square cells of varying sizes d . For each grid size, the number of cells $N(d)$ intersecting the object is counted. Plotting $\log N(d)$ against $\log(1/d)$ produces a linear relationship whose slope corresponds to the fractal dimension:

$$D = \frac{\log N(d)}{\log\left(\frac{1}{d}\right)} \quad (1)$$

We developed and tested a vector-based implementation in ArcGIS Pro using Python and vector and raster-based implementations in R. Our approaches calculate horizontal and vertical fractal dimension separately. For the horizontal fractal dimension, the trail was analyzed in map view, while the vertical fractal dimension was derived from its elevation profile. To improve the robustness of regression analysis, the grid size was reduced iteratively by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$ (Gonzato et al. 2000). The minimum box size corresponded to one meter, or to the smallest feasible subdivision obtained through successive $\sqrt{2}$ reductions.

In the raster R workflow, segments were rasterized at progressively finer cell sizes corresponding to those reported above. The box counting procedure was further enhanced by evaluating each trail segment across multiple rotation angles (0° – 45° in 5° increments) to reduce grid orientation bias.

2.2 GIS/Python and R implementation

A series of eleven short Python scripts were developed to address each step in the methodology for calculating fractal dimension for a set of lines. Constructing independent scripts offered two advantages: first, processing and algorithms for each stage could be tested and validated separately, and second, processing could be split into separate runs, which is useful for large feature sets. For the R implementation, the box counting algorithm was applied using a raster-based approach in which each trail segment was rasterized at multiple cell resolutions. This approach was approximately 200 times faster than the vector-based line-grid intersection technique and was therefore used in the R analysis.

Figure 1 shows the complexity of Slovenian relief, spanning four macro-regions. The 307 trail segments that were a subject of the analysis with R approach are relatively evenly distributed among all of Slovenia. Due to slower computer processing only 42 of 307 segments were included in the second analysis, combining ArcGIS Pro and Python. The complete results from both approaches are presented below with figures, but for brevity only 15 of 42 segments are listed in Table 1.

To evaluate the proposed fractal analysis approach, five synthetic line geometries were generated in R—a horizontal line, a diagonal line, and Koch curves of orders 2, 6, and 8—each stored as a separate geographic feature (Figure 2). All geometries were processed using the horizontal fractal dimension estimation method in both ArcGIS/Python and R, and the resulting values were compared to assess consistency between the two workflows.

Figure 1. Slovenia's four macro-regions: Pannonian, Dinaric, Mediterranean, and Alpine. The selected 307 trail segments are in orange, the selected 42 segments are black, and selected 15 segments are in turquoise, labeled with ID_Path numbers.

Figure 2. Five synthetic line geometries—a horizontal line, a diagonal line, and Koch curves of orders 2, 6, and 8—were generated in R, saved as feature classes, and projected to EPSG 3794. These features were then used to test the ArcGIS/Python and R models.

3 Results

3.1 Results of R and GIS/Python Implementations

3.1.1 R workflow ($N = 307$)

The R based analysis included 307 trail segments from Slovenia's hiking trail network. Horizontal and vertical fractal dimension values were computed for each segment, with all macro regions and difficulty classes represented. Difficulty classes are established by the Alpine Association of Slovenia (Planinska zveza Slovenije) and are based on qualitative expert evaluation. Figure 3 illustrates the relationship between horizontal and vertical fractal dimensions for all 307 segments. Clear structural patterns emerge: Easy trails tend to cluster in the lower left portion of the plot, while Very Difficult trails are distributed across multiple regions of fractal dimension space. Vertical fractal dimension values above 1.1 are rare, whereas higher horizontal values are comparatively common, suggesting that high vertical ruggedness either occurs infrequently in

Figure 3. Relationship between horizontal and vertical fractal dimensions of 307 trail segments. Points are individual segments. Colors indicate difficulty class and labels denote acro-regions (A: Alpine, D: Dinaric, P: Pannonian, M: Mediterranean).

the landscape or is typically avoided by trail designers. Of the 307 segments analyzed in R, a subset of 42 was also evaluated using the ArcGIS/Python workflow for direct comparison.

3.1.2 ArcGIS/Python workflow (N = 42)

Table 1 summarizes the 42 trail segments analyzed using ArcGIS Pro/Python. The R based values for the same 42 segments are included for comparison. The two methods produce systematically different estimates, with the R values consistently higher. Several segments show fractal

dimension values below 1, which is theoretically impossible for linear features and indicates methodological sensitivity. Figure 4 visualizes the same relationship for the GIS/Python workflow. A positive linear trend is evident across difficulty classes and macro-regions, although substantial scatter around the regression line reflects considerable unexplained variability, the regression model is statistically significant ($p=0.0009$) but explains only 24.3% of the variance, indicating that the two metrics share a weak association. Two trail segments classified as Very Difficult appear in the

Table 1. Excerpt of 15 trail segments from the dataset of horizontal and vertical fractal dimension values calculated for all 42 segments. The table compares results obtained using two analytical approaches: ArcGIS with Python and R.

ID_Path	Macror.	Diffic.	FD horizon.	FD vertical	FD horizon.	FD vertical
186	Mediterranean	Very difficult	1.196	1.049	1.292	1.075
1681	Alpine	Difficult	1.082	1.016	1.110	1.025
1752	Alpine	Very difficult	1.040	1.116	1.057	1.110
1959	Alpine	Easy	1.182	1.025	1.228	1.059
3513	Dinaric	Difficult	1.182	1.048	1.300	1.106
3887	Alpine	Easy	1.107	1.009	1.130	1.027
4171	Dinaric	Easy	1.112	1.008	1.116	1.047
5211	Pannonian	Easy	1.076	1.005	1.088	1.031
6021	Pannonian	Difficult	1.051	0.948	1.106	1.061
9118	Dinaric	Very difficult	1.190	1.084	1.270	1.164
12489	Alpine	Very difficult	1.143	1.034	1.225	1.029
12851	Alpine	Difficult	1.075	1.033	1.080	1.045
14018	Pannonian	Very difficult	1.144	1.046	1.235	1.029
16312	Mediterranean	Easy	1.068	1.000	1.075	1.047
127399	Mediterranean	Difficult	1.092	1.006	1.108	1.023

lower-left portion of the plot, making them among the least rugged trails in the dataset, this suggests that factors beyond geometric ruggedness might contribute to their difficulty rating. The R and ArcGIS/Python workflows produced similar structural patterns but consistently different magnitudes.

The R workflow yielded slightly higher estimates across both dimensions. These deviations likely reflect differences in implementation: the R method uses a raster-based algorithm with multiple rotation angles (0°–45° in 5° increments), whereas the ArcGIS/Python method applies a single orientation vector grid intersection approach.

Figure 4. Relationship between horizontal and vertical fractal dimensions of 42 trail segments. Points are individual segments. Colors indicate difficulty class and labels denote macro-regions (A: Alpine, D: Dinaric, P: Pannonian, M: Mediterranean). Solid line shows the linear regression model ($R^2 = 0.243$, $p = 0.0009$).

3.2 Results of testing the two approaches on synthetic curves

The synthetic geometries provide controlled test cases with known theoretical properties. The fractal dimension of a straight line is 1, whereas the analytical fractal dimension of the Koch curve is 1.2618 (Gonzato 1998). The

Table 2. Estimated horizontal fractal dimension values for five synthetic lines using two approaches: ArcGIS/Python, and R.

ID_Path	Type of line	ArcGIS with Python	R
		FD horizontal	FD horizontal
1	Horizontal line	0.990	1.030
2	Diagonal line	1.048	1.010
3	Koch curve of order 2	1.072	1.086
4	Koch curve of order 6	1.238	1.264
5	Koch curve of order 8	1.281	1.306

resulting slope coefficients, representing the estimated horizontal fractal dimension, are summarized in Table 3.

Both approaches captured the expected increase in fractal dimension with increasing geometric complexity. In the ArcGIS/Python workflow, the horizontal and diagonal lines produced values of 0.990 and 1.048, respectively, while the Koch curves increased from 1.072 (order 2) to 1.281 (order 8). The latter aligns with previous findings that box counting can slightly overestimate the fractal dimension of Koch type curves, especially when box sizes are coarse relative to geometric detail (Rian and Sassone 2014). The R workflow showed the same pattern but produced slightly higher estimates overall: 1.030 and 1.010 for the horizontal and diagonal lines, and 1.086 to 1.306 for the Koch curves.

4 Discussion

In this study, the box counting algorithm for estimating the fractal dimension of linear geographic features was implemented in both R and ArcGIS Pro/Python and evaluated using synthetic and real-world trail geometries. The synthetic experiments confirm that the algorithm responds predictably to increasing geometric irregularity.

They also reveal non negligible estimation error, consistent with previous findings that box counting is susceptible to distortions when applied to discretized or low-resolution linear features (Douglass 2025). Several estimated fractal dimension values fall below 1, which can be attributed to discretization artifacts that flatten the regression slope.

Comparison of the two workflows highlights systematic methodological differences. R consistently returns slightly higher estimates than ArcGIS/Python for both synthetic and real-world data. Although both methods correctly capture relative differences in geometric complexity, the magnitude varies, likely due to differences between the raster based and vector-based implementations, including their respective grid handling and parameter settings. Future work will quantify these differences to better understand bias and variability. For large problems, by far greater computational efficiency of the raster-based algorithm makes it preferable, but the algorithm requires refinement to improve its accuracy.

The real-world trail analysis reinforces the precision issues observed in the synthetic experiments, as results from R diverge consistently from ArcGIS/Python. Even so, characterizing trails with horizontal and vertical fractal dimensions reveals meaningful patterns in trail morphology and the design trade-offs encountered in different landscapes. For example, two Very Difficult trails appear among the least rugged in Figure 3, suggesting that difficulty classifications might incorporate factors beyond geometric complexity, such as for example exposure or hazard.

Finally, the broader analysis in R (N=307) shows notable structural patterns: vertical fractal dimension values above 1.1 are rare, whereas horizontal values above 1.1 are more common. This may indicate that extreme vertical ruggedness is either uncommon in natural terrain or intentionally avoided during trail design. Promising directions for future research include exploring nonlinear

relationships between fractal dimensions, landscape context, and trail difficulty.

5 Conclusions

This study evaluated the usefulness of horizontal and vertical fractal dimensions for characterizing real world linear geographic features. Slovenian hiking trails provided an ideal test environment due to their large topographic variability. While the box counting algorithm proved sensitive to discretization, feature alignment, and parameter choices, the two implementations tested—R and ArcGIS/Python—consistently revealed similar structural patterns despite differences in absolute values. Although neither approach demonstrated high numerical precision, the resulting fractal dimension estimates offer meaningful insight into trail characteristics and the design trade-offs that arise in complex landscapes, highlighting the potential of fractal metrics as complementary descriptors of trail geometry and the need for improved estimation techniques in future research.

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6 References

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